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Identifying Normativity in Word Stress and Intonation of English

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ABSTRACT

This paper aims at exploring the normative rules used to accentuate prominent syllables in English words as well as prominent words in English sentences. As part of findings, the study has identified seven prominent normative rules of word stress and seven prominent rules.

Keywords: Word Stress, Intonation, Normativity

INTRODUCTION

While learning a language we learn mainly three things of that language. Number one is vocabulary; number two is structure or grammar in which we learn how words are combined together to write or to speak a meaningful sentence; and number three is pronunciation which perhaps is the most important component of mastering a language. But English being English is somewhat weird in terms of pronunciations. One of the main reasons of using wrong pronunciations in English is English words are not pronounced the way they are written. In this regard, speakers of languages like Sanskrit, Hindi, Spanish, and many other Indian languages are really fortunate because they don't have to learn pronunciation additionally. In what follows, we can see first how English pronunciation is asymmetrical in nature.

However, this study has identified 14 normative principles of word stress and intonation.